

Analysis of the Leadership Role on Employee Well-being. Study Case: HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta

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ABSTRACT: Employee well-being is high on the corporate agenda because companies and their boards of directors connect and correlate it with success. Employees' eligibility for perks, insurance, and medical care is frequently determined by socioeconomic considerations. This means that disadvantaged groups are frequently left behind, although they require the most assistance. HKBP or Huria Kristen Batak Protestan is one of the largest church organizations among Protestant churches in Indonesia and Southeast Asia. As one of the largest churches in this country, HKBP should be an organization that can set an example in terms of organizational governance that is characterized by being clean, transparent, visionary, has access to the public, and is based on the needs of the congregation. But the hope to be an example, an example organizationally has not been realized properly because of turmoil from internal problems that went wrong.

Currently, by looking at HKBP's internals, it has even caused turmoil, and many inequalities and made HKBP's management far from what we expected. There are even terms for HKBP wetland and dryland HKBP. Of course, this fact cannot be denied, even though all HKBP servants have made promises to be willing to be placed anywhere to preach the gospel. The struggle for churches that are wetlands and those who have financial resources is certainly one of the evaluation materials and a weakness of HKBP's financial decentralization, where this does not at all reflect the life of God's servants who should receive the assigned placement for each individual. This also shows that well-being is not evenly distributed and creates gaps among servants.

This study aims to identify leadership roles to employee well-being, such as Job Performance, Ethics or Personal Characteristics, Communication or Feedback, and Justice or Fairness. To determine what has to be addressed and developed by leaders to improve the well-being of employees in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta can be seen from a leadership role on employee well-being indicators, such as Positive Emotions, Engagement, Relationship or Positive Relationships, Meaning, and Achievement (PERMA). Based on this research, the priority that must be improved in Leadership is Justice or Fairness. HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta has to level up and maintain the existing program, such as seminars about self-development in leadership and annual programs to intensify the bond between the leader and fellow church ministries.

KEYWORDS: Employee Well-being, Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

HKBP or Huria Kristen Batak Protestan is the third largest religious organization in Indonesia after Nahdlatul Ulama and Muhammadiyah. This organization is a church with a Protestant Christian denomination that inherits the traditions of the Lutheran and Reformed churches. The vision of HKBP is to be a blessing to the world and their mission is to worship the Holy Trinity, preach the gospel to the congregation and to those who drifted away from the church, be the salt that illuminates Batak, Indonesian, and global culture, and restoring the dignity of the underprivileged and marginalized through education, health, and community economic empowerment. As one of the largest churches in this country, HKBP should be an organization that can set an example in terms of organizational governance that is characterized by being clean, transparent, visionary, has access to the public, and is based on the needs of the congregation. Why not, HKBP has the capital for this with the support of highly qualified human resources, starting from the level of priests, *bibelvrouw*, deaconesses, and *guru huria*. But the hope to be an example, an example organizationally has not been realized properly because of turmoil from internal problems that went wrong. Currently, by looking at HKBP's internals, it has even caused turmoil, where the financial decentralization model previously used by HKBP created many inequalities and had weaknesses that made HKBP's governance far from what we expected. This also shows that well-being is not evenly distributed and creates gaps among servants. This is the background and purpose of this research, where the role of the HKBP leadership is to improve the well-being of job recipients (servants), especially for HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta. Based on SK

No: 541/L08/IV/2021, HKBP is working to enhance the well-being of its staff members who work as servants of God. The management of the HKBP centralized concept is built on the following values: Equality, Justice, Sustainable, and Fraternity. We could infer from the principles above that financial centralization is a management grand design based on the needs of job receivers in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta, with a broad vision and a strong institutional foundation. This is also intended to be able to solve any difficulties within the HKBP, ultimately strengthening its internal structure as a religious institution. Based on this shift in the system, the author is curious about the impact of HKBP leaders who are directly involved in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta on the well-being of the servants who are human resources on duty in the district in question, particularly after the centralization system was implemented in January 2023. Of course, since the adoption of this new system, there have been important improvements that have contributed to the well-being of priests, *bibelvrouw*, deaconesses, and *guru huria* who work in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Leadership

According to Munson in Hutahaean (2021:2), leadership is having the capacity to manage people in such a way that the greatest results are achieved with the least amount of conflict and as much cooperation as feasible. According to Siagian in Hutahaean (2021: 2), leadership is also a skill and ability of someone who has occupied the position of being a leader in a job in influencing the actions of other people, particularly his subordinates, in such a way that this positive behavior can make a real contribution in achieving organizational goals. Based on the definitions that have been described, it can be understood that leadership is a form of ability to influence, encourage, and invite others to do something to achieve common goals. According to Cohen (2011: 9), leadership serves a purpose that is directly tied to social situations in each organization's life. When making decisions, the leadership must consider the social context of the company so that the decision is a shared responsibility, including its implementation. Good leaders draw others, who are delighted to do their best to help their leaders succeed. The following are the dimensions of leadership according to Koscec (2007: 210), namely:

1. Functional Dimension:

- a. Job Performance: Gives me the latitude that I need to do my job to the best of my abilities, ensures that I have the right skills and knowledge to do my job to the best of my abilities, supports me to develop myself for future advancement opportunities, provides me with clear performance expectations, and reviews my job performance at least once a year
- b. Communication or Feedback: Listens with an open mind, recognizes or praises me whenever I do a good job, keeps me regularly informed on important issues, and provides me with ongoing feedback on my work

2. Values Dimension:

- a. Ethics or Personal Characteristics: Leads by example and action, someone I can trust and talk with openly without the fear of reprisal, keeps promises and stands by commitments made, and acts decisively and gets things done
- b. Justice or Fairness: Treats me with respect, resolves conflict pretty and appropriately, treats everyone equally - does not play favorites, recommends new ideas from our work unit up to senior management, gives credit to the whole work unit when receiving positive feedback on our performance, fair when reviewing my performance, and take appropriate action against people who under-perform

B. Employee Well-Being

According to Seligman (2012: 9), well-being is a construct and happiness is a thing. A "real thing" is a directly measurable entity. Such an entity can be "operationalized", meaning a particular set of measures defines it. Utamaningsih and Siagian in Busro (2018: 118), explain that the well-being of workers is strongly influenced by the level of income and other income earned while working. According to the opinion of Busro (2018: 119), to measure well-being not just in terms of income, but also in terms of other aspects, including living conditions, a home and all of its possessions, access to information and technology, and assets like cash, gold, furniture, and other moveable and immovable items. The Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD) in Bradford Diocesan Academies Trust (2016: 1), defined employee well-being as creating an environment to promote a state of contentment that allows an employee to flourish and achieve their full potential for the benefit themselves and their organization. In Pawar (2019: 28), Wilson et.al stated that employee well-being is another important outcome to seek for an organization. Specifically, the definition of a healthy organization. According to Wilson et.al, a healthy organization makes deliberate, methodical, and cooperative

efforts to maximize worker productivity and well-being through well-designed and fulfilling jobs, a welcoming social workplace, and open and equitable opportunities for career and work-life enhancement. In Seligman (2012: 10-11), numerous factors that contribute to well-being lead us away from monism. It is essentially a theory of free will, and its five components describe what self-determined individuals will select. Each aspect of well-being must have three properties to count as an element: 1) It contributes to well-being, 2) Many people pursue it for its own sake, not merely to get any of the other elements, and 3) It is defined and measured independently of the other elements (exclusivity). Well-being theory has five (5) dimensions and each of the five has those three properties, there are:

1. Positive emotions: A vital component of well-being is experiencing pleasant emotions. People who are content with their lives enjoy the past and hope for the future and the present. Humans require positive feelings like hope, happiness, connection, love, and tranquility to feel good.
2. Engagement: The term "engagement" describes a psychological bond with a task or a group of people, such as a sense of pervasiveness, interest, or involvement in daily activities. Concentrate on what is being done while experiencing genuine joy and complete absorption in it. Both my personal and professional lives flow well.
3. Relationships or Positive Relationships: Feelings of social integration, compassion and support, and happiness with interpersonal interactions are all examples of positive partnerships. Strong ties to one's family, friends, and neighbors are essential for everyone. One essential component of well-being is having healthy relationships.
4. Meaning: The idea that one's life has a purpose and one feels connected to a higher power. The finest kind of life is one where you can make a significant contribution to a larger cause and affect others as well as oneself, making life more meaningful.
5. Achievement: Achievement includes making progress toward goals, being able to carry out daily tasks, and feeling successful. Goals can be achieved, whether they are modest, medium, or enormous, depending on the person. The handy mnemonic of those five (5) elements is called PERMA. No one element defines well-being, but each contributes to it.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, the issue of "Analysis of the Leadership Role on Employee Well-being" is raised. Study Case: HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta. Variable X, which is Leadership, serves as the independent variable in this study whereas variable Y, which is Employee Well-being, serves as the dependent variable. For the Leadership variable, the author adopts a theory from Koscec (2007:210) and for the Employee Well-being theory, the authors apply Seligman (2012:10–11). For data processing in this study, the application program SPSS 25 (Statistical Package for Social Science 25) would be used. The relationship model of this research is stated below:

Figure II.1 Relationship Model of Leadership and Employee Well-being

Source: Author (2023)

From the relationship model between Leadership Role as the variable X and Employee Well-being as the variable Y, we can know all of the hypotheses that emerged in this study. The following is a description of these hypotheses:

- H01: Job Performance of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
- H1: Job Performance of Leadership, **has** a significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.

- H02: Job Performance of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H2: Job Performance of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H03: Job Performance of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H3: Job Performance of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H04: Job Performance of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H4: Job Performance of Leadership **has** a significant effect on Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H05: Job Performance of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.
H5: Job Performance of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.
H06: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
H6: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
H07: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H7: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H08: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H8: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H09: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H9: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H010: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.
H10: Communication or Feedback of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.
H011: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have no** significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
H11: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have** a significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
H012: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have no** significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H12: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have** a significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H013: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have no** significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H13: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have** a significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H014: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have no** significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H14: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have** a significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H015: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have no** significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.
H15: Ethics or Personal Characteristics of Leadership **have** a significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.
H016: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
H16: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Positive Emotions of Employee Well-being.
H017: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H17: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Engagement of Employee Well-being.
H018: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H18: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Relationship or Positive Relationship of Employee Well-being.
H019: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H19: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Meaning of Employee Well-being.
H020: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has no** significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.

H20: Justice or Fairness of Leadership **has** a significant effect on the Achievement of Employee Well-being.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses 2 (two) data types, namely: Primary Data and Secondary Data. According to Hermawan, Asep (2005: 168), primary data is data collected directly by researchers to answer problems or research objectives conducted in exploratory, descriptive, and causal research using data collection methods in the form of surveys or observations. Secondary data is a historical data structure regarding variables that have been collected and compiled previously by other parties. In understanding the leadership role on employee well-being, the authors used a quantitative method and used a research instrument in the form of an online questionnaire that was distributed to respondents who work as servants of God or church ministries in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta. This is done by the author as a method of data collection. The questions asked are closed, therefore respondents can choose answers that are already available in the distributed questionnaire.

VALIDITY TEST

Each item in the leadership roles variable is based on 14 statements and employee well-being on 16 statements is declared acceptable and all of them fit with the conditions, where all of the R Count is greater than the R Table (0,182).

RELIABILITY TEST

The technique used in testing the reliability of this study is Cronbach's Alpha technique. According to Siregar (2010: 173), Alpha Cronbach is a technique or formula that can be used to determine whether a research instrument is reliable or not. According to Ghozali (2016: 47), reliability is a tool for measuring a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable or construct. A questionnaire is said to be reliable or reliable if one's answers to statements are consistent or stable from time to time. According to Nunally in Ghozali (2016: 48), a construct or variable is said to be reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value ≥ 0.70 . Based on the result, it is shown that Cronbach's Alpha of Leadership Roles (0.902) and Employee Well-being (0.929) are bigger than 0,70. Therefore, it can be concluded that the instruments of Leadership Roles and Employee Well-being are reliable.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

To facilitate the author in describing and analyzing the influence matrix, the following table presents a summary of all dimensions of leadership on employee well-being outcome:

Table IV.38

Average Variable Score and Influence on Employee Well-being

Variable	Label	Avg.	Influence					Sig.
			Positive Emotions	Engagement	Relationship	Meaning	Achievement	
Job Performance	X1	4,11	0,358	0,464	0,377	0,345	0,429	0,000
	X2	4,15						
	X3	4,09						
Communication or Feedback	X4	4,17	0,306	0,370	0,420	0,377	0,385	0,000
	X5	4,16						
	X6	4,17						
Ethics or Personal Characteris	X7	4,21	0,449	0,642	0,496	0,442	0,446	0,000
	X8	4,20						
	X9	4,12						
Justice or Fairness	X10	4,18	0,704	0,881	0,599	0,668	0,664	0,000
	X11	4,33						
	X12	4,39						
	X13	4,31						
	X14	4,28						

Source: IBM SPSS 25

In this study, the author refers to Table IV.38 in compiling and mapping the influence score matrix and variable score. The author also maps the questionnaire questions into 9 (nine) quadrants based on the mapping of each score and influence. The aim is to provide improvements to the priority areas identified by the company. For example, the indicator of the Job Performance variable is mapped into Quadrant 1, which means that this quadrant has a high influence on employee well-being outcomes but has a low variable score. This becomes the priority for the company to make improvements. This approach also facilitates the author in analyzing and mapping variables. The same process is applied to the subsequent quadrants. Furthermore, to calculate the average values of the variables, the author calculates the scores for each questionnaire and each dimension of all the questionnaires. The influence score is obtained using statistical analysis with SPSS 25. Each quadrant is symbolized by the sequence number of the questionnaire. For example, X1 represents the indicator of Job Performance from the Leadership variable that will be mapped in a specific quadrant.

Table IV.37

Comparison Between Leadership on Employee Well-being

Ranking	Positive Emotions	Engagement	Relationship	Meaning	Achievement
1 (Most Influencing)	Justice or Fairness				
2	Ethics or Personal Characteristics				
3	Job Performance	Job Performance	Communication or Feedback	Communication or Feedback	Job Performance
Least Influencing	Communication or Feedback	Communication or Feedback	Job Performance	Job Performance	Communication or Feedback

Source: IBM SPSS 25

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the table is a ranking table created to assist the author in determining which variables should be prioritized for maintenance or improvement in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta, to improve employee well-being. Analyzing this ranking matrix is an important step in selecting factors based on questionnaire results and summaries.

ORGANIZATION SOLUTION

1. Leadership towards Positive Emotions

It can be seen that the top priority is the Justice or Fairness of the Leadership variable, referring to X13 with an average score of 4.33 and X14 with an average score of 4.28, those are aligned with the beta value indicating high influence towards “Positive Emotions” of Employee Well-being. Both labels refer to Justice or Fairness indicator. In this case, the organization needs to provide programs such as seminars to enhance leadership skills annually with targeted programs. The organization has to hold a yearly event between the leader and employees (church ministries). This activity is expected to train sensitivity skills and enhance teamwork among the organization members, so the employee well-being of the organization can increase. According to Page in Hudin (2012; 5), the feeling of achievement at work is a certain achievement that they feel related to work, when employees feel happy with what they are doing they give a feeling of achievement because they have been able to succeed in achieving the goals set in their work. This can increase the well-being of every individual who plays a role in the organization. By voicing recommendations and ideas sparked in work units to senior management, positive emotions felt by employees can increase and make performance more productive. Awards given to employees at work are rewards that aim to give praise or more enthusiasm so that individuals can improve their performance even better. It also aims to prove that the leadership is fair in reviewing employee performance.

2. Leadership toward Engagement

It can be seen that the top priority is the Justice or Fairness of the Leadership variable, referring to X14 with an average score of 4.28 and it aligns with its beta value indicating high influence towards “Engagement” of Employee Well-being. Label X14

refers to Justice or Fairness indicator. In this case, the organization needs to provide programs such as seminars to enhance leadership skills annually with targeted programs. The organization has to hold a yearly event between the leader and employees (church ministries). This activity is expected to train sensitivity skills and enhance teamwork among the organization members, so the employee well-being of the organization can increase. Rajagukguk and Vera (2023:15) stated that the organization can maximize employee well-being by applying the values of justice and equality based on class, length of service, position, and providing qualified benefits. Every active and diligent employee (church ministries) needs to be given appreciation in the form of awards with additional incentives. It also aims to prove that the leadership is fair in reviewing employee performance.

3. Leadership toward Relationship or Positive Relationships

It can be seen that the top priority is the Justice or Fairness of the Leadership variable, referring to X14 with an average score of 4.28 and it aligns with its beta value indicating high influence towards "Relationship or Positive Relationships" of Employee Well-being. Label X14 refers to Justice or Fairness indicator. Based on the Quadrant V characteristics which are medium influence and medium score, the organization needs to conduct observations for the leader and employees (church ministries). Based on Adiwena, et al. (2016:139) stated that the relationship between the organization member (church ministries) can maximize employee well-being because the presence of colleagues in the community is the "closest family member", to share and support each other amidst the number of challenges they have to face. The community becomes a source of strength in their life as God's servant. As a result, it can be seen that the Relationship or Positive Relationship indicator is not necessary for the Justice or Fairness from Leadership variable indicator to function. Organizations must make observations, nevertheless, to show that the leader is concerned about the church ministries from the standpoint of relationships or positive relationships.

4. Leadership towards Meaning

It can be seen that the top priority is the Justice or Fairness of the Leadership variable, referring to X11 with an average score of 4.33, X13 with an average score of 4.31, and X14 with an average score of 4.28, those are aligned with the beta value indicating high influence towards "Meaning" of Employee Well-being. Labels X11, X13, and X14 refer to Justice or Fairness indicator. Based on the Quadrant V characteristics which are medium influence and medium score, the organization needs to conduct observations for the leader and employees (church ministries). According to Waltermann in Adiwena et.al (2016:139-140), being content in your materialistic life and being happy are not the only components of well-being. More than that, happiness is a state attained via the alignment or congruence of one's actions with their values. They have been imbued with a passion for service that is both a method of achieving well-being and not an impediment or danger to it. Although service may not always go smoothly, the church ministry's numerous "assets"—self-determination, knowledge and skill, coping mechanisms, and social support—allow them to keep striving for well-being. The Meaning indicator is located in Quadrant V, where the influence is moderate with an average score and this quadrant is not the top priority for the organization.

5. Leadership towards Achievement

It can be seen that the top priority is the Justice or Fairness of the Leadership variable, referring to X11 with an average score of 4.33, X13 with an average score of 4.31, and X14 with an average score of 4.28, those are aligned with the beta value indicating high influence towards "Achievement" of Employee Well-being. Labels X11, X13, and X14 refer to Justice or Fairness indicator. Based on the Quadrant V characteristics which are medium influence and medium score, the organization needs to conduct observations for the leader and employees (church ministries). According to Rajagukguk and Vera (2023:15), HKBP has a value of Justice in its policy to support the well-being of church ministries. This policy aims to provide appreciation in the form of additional incentives for every waiter who performs his service well. This also aims to support the survival of the family of church servants. The Achievement indicator is located in Quadrant V, where the influence is moderate with an average score and this quadrant is not the top priority for the organization.

SUMMARY OF THE LEADERSHIP ROLE ON EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING

Based on the influence matrix and variable scores above, it can be concluded that the top priority faced by HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta in terms of Positive Emotions, Engagement, Relationship or Positive Relationships, Meaning, and Achievement of Employee Well-being is related to the Justice or Fairness dimension of Leadership. To enhance employee well-being, there are several things that HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta has to do for the organization.

HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta needs to conduct observations and creates some plan to improve their church ministries' well-being. If the organization can improve this factor, it will not only enhance employee well-being in facing the ministries' duties. As an organization, HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta should be able to take some initiative plans and implement programs to enhance employee well-being. This can be done by organizing seminars about leadership for all church ministries, so the leadership skill able to improve and also enhance the bond between the leader and fellow church ministries in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta.

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Based on the objectives mentioned in Chapter I of this research, the implementation plan focuses on boosting and encouraging Positive Emotions, Engagement, Relationship or Positive Relationships, Meaning, and Achievement from the employee well-being variable of HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta. The indicator of Justice or Fairness is a part of the organization's Leadership role and becomes the most significant function to be enhanced and to boost the employee's (church ministries) well-being, so that the organization's purpose of supporting their employee well-being may be met. The plans are as follows:

Table IV.44

Implementation Plan and Justification

Indicator	Program	Activity	Output
Justice or Fairness	Organizing a self-development seminar and training to enhance Leadership skills.	Providing a seminar and training to all church ministries to understanding and enhancing their leadership skill.	To intensify a leader's sensitivity skills the importance of enhancing employee (church ministries) well-being and developing a strong bond between a leader and fellow church ministries.

With the proposed programs above, the author hopes that the implementation plan can be successfully realized by the organization, where all the respondents in this research are people who work as servants of God or ministers in the church. The author also hopes for raising awareness of the importance of the leadership role in enhancing employees' well-being in a religious organization.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the statistical analysis described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that there is a significant role of leadership that affected employee well-being. This will affect the organizational performance in doing their vision and mission as a church that has many congregations. There is a significant difference in the employee well-being indicators: Positive Emotions, Engagement, Relationship or Positive Relationships, Meaning, and Achievement on Leadership Role's dimensions, especially in Justice or Fairness. From the result of the influence and variable score matrix, it can be concluded that the current conditions being faced by HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta are almost spread to all quadrants. Based on the description described in chapter 4 (four), the priority that must be improved in Leadership is Justice or Fairness to enhance employee well-being and as an organization, HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta has to level up and maintain the existing program, such as seminars about self-development in

leadership and annual programs to intensify the bond between the leader and fellows church ministries. By improving the Justice or Fairness indicator as the critical area, employee well-being will be enhanced and HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta is capable to ensure their church ministries have a balanced life while doing the church's vision and mission to the congregation, as their main profession.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions regarding the Analysis of the Leadership Role on Employee Well-being. Case Study: HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta, the authors apply the following suggestions:

a. Academic Recommendation:

This research is expected to be a lesson for further researchers. Future researchers are advised to conduct qualitative research because the authors have conducted this research quantitatively. The next writer can also connect leadership with other variables besides employee well-being. In addition, a psychological approach can raise this topic better because it relates to the role of leadership in an organization and employee well-being, or a theological approach because this research is associated with a religious organization.

b. Practical Recommendation:

Leadership role greatly influences employee well-being in HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta. Even though HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta is a religious organization, HKBP District DKI Jakarta is not immune from problems that often occur in companies and organizations in general. In this study, it can be seen that one of the indicators of the Leadership role, namely: Justice or Fairness, obtains high results compared to other indicators and makes this indicator a matter that greatly influences the well-being of the church ministries that have a role as employees in the organization.

Based on this, the authors hope that HKBP District VIII DKI Jakarta will provide leadership training in the form of seminars and self-development activities to train a leader's sensitivity in leading an organization and strengthen a leader's bond with those He/She leads. Through this, employees who work as servants of God or church servants can feel the embrace of a leader and can succeed in the well-being program from the HKBP Center in Tarutung, North Sumatra.

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